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Principles & Practice of Extensive Reading

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ABSTRACT

Starting or revamping an Extensive Reading (ER) program can be a daunting task. There are several factors to consider, including reading materials, objectives, grades, and the role of the teacher among others. Richard Day and Julian Bamford (2002) have outlined ten fundamental principles of ER but how can they be used to implement an ER program from the ground up? This article discusses these ten principles of ER and suggests how they can be practically applied when planning an ER program, as well as provides tips for avoiding pitfalls encountered when planning/implementing an ER course. (95 words)

I. Introduction

Extensive Reading (ER) comes in many shapes and forms. A single definition is hard to come by but in 1990 Susser and Robb summarized various research into their working definition of “reading (a) of large quantities of material or long texts; (b) for global or general understanding; (c) with the intention of obtaining pleasure from the text” (Susser& Robb, 1990, p.165). The definition has since been expanded and explained in more details and Richard Day and Julian Bamford (2002) have listed ten fundamental principles of ER. The Day and Bamford principles were inspired by Williams (1986) and have been developed over the considerable time they have been involved in researching and promoting ER. This article will discuss these ten principles and suggest how they can be practically applied when planning an ER program, as well as provide tips for avoiding pitfalls encountered when planning/implementing an ER course.

II. Top Ten Principles for Teaching Extensive Reading

These are the top ten principles as originally listed by (Bamford& Day (2002).

- 1 The reading material is easy
- 2 A variety of reading material on a wide range of topics must be available
- 3 Learners choose what they want to read
- 4 Learners read as much as possible
- 5The purpose of reading is usually related to pleasure, information and general understanding
- 6 Reading is its own reward
- 7 Reading speed is usually faster rather than slower
- 8 Reading is individual and silent
- 9 Teachers orient and guide their students
- 10 The teacher is a role model of a reader

When the list was published in 2002, two responses where published in the same issue of *Reading in a Foreign Language* (Prowse, 2002, and Robb, 2002). Whilst Prowse mainly concurs with Day and Bamford, he also advocates the use of recordings, Robb disagrees with the 6th principle ‘Reading is its own reward’. He claims that there need to be some kind of control function and that reading “to satisfy a course requirement” might be necessary in order to motivate students to continue to read (Robb, 2002, p. 146).

1. Issues and Advice

The ten ER principles are a good starting point but when putting them into practice some issues arise, especially when it comes the reading material, covered by principle 1 and 2, and the purpose, principle 5and6.

1) Reading Material

In addition to Day and Bamford’s principles of easy and varied material, Williams claims that “*In the absence of interesting texts, very little is possible*” (1986, p. 42)and Prowse (2002) stresses that texts should be easy and engaging. This makes selecting books one of the most crucial aspects of any ER program. In the author’s experience, the largest difficulties have been in securing enough funds and convincing faculty and staff to supply material that is easy enough for the students. It is recommended that there should be few or no unfamiliar items of vocabulary. Hu and Nation (2002) state it is

necessary for readers to have a 98% coverage rate of the vocabulary. However, this may mean that some college students should be reading very simple texts, such as *Reading Foundation Library* or even *Building Blocks Library*. Both these series are excellent for lower level students but were rejected to be purchased by a mid-level private university in Japan due to being deemed beneath university level. As a result, the author had to use his private funds as well as donated samples to secure enough books at an appropriate level for the ER program. Once students are able to read at the 200-250 headword level the choice of material greatly increases, but it can still be a challenge to have your institution purchase enough books. Having students buy and donate books and using library or material budgets are other ways of securing funds (see more suggestions in Waring, 2000). For a successful program you need to have a minimum of three books per student in the program, preferably more (Extensive Reading Foundation [ERF], 2011). There is also a lot of free materials available that can inspire and improve your ER program (Fuisting, 2010).

Following the principles of having a variety of topics and engaging material is getting easier with more and more material being published for the EFL market. The Language Learner Literature (LLL) awards, administrated by the Extensive Reading Foundation, can serve as a good guide to high quality books written for learners of English. An excellent example of a low level but extremely engaging, and sadly always current topic, is Phil Prowse's *Why?* (2008). It deals with the subject of war but is written at a beginner level of 250 headwords. In terms of variety, it is recommended to include several publishers' series, and both fiction and non-fiction, original stories and adaptations, as well as a variety of genres (ERF, 2011).

2) Purpose

Day and Bamford (2002) state 'Reading is its own reward' and other ER advocates (Prowse, 2002; Williams, 1986) strongly discourage the use of the quizzes and other forms of tests to check if students have read the books they claim to have completed. Book talks, reviews and discussions could instead be used to measure if the students have engaged with the book (Bamford & Day, 2003). Depending on the nature of the class this approach might be suitable. However, most educational institutions require some kind of control function and it can be argued that passing a quiz and thereby increasing the number of words read can be motivational (Robb, 2002). In the author's experience the Moodle Reader, developed by Tom Robb at Kyoto Sangyo University, Japan, is one of the best and easiest to use ER monitoring systems. It can be used for individual classes or institutional wide ER programs. It covers and impressive 3000+ graded readers and books for young readers and is based on the amount of words read

(see www.moodlereader.org).

III. Conclusion

The principles stated by Day and Bamford are a very good guide and inspiration for how to do ER but each educator should look at his or her situation and adapt these principles as necessary. The students' and the institution's needs and capabilities should be taken into account when deciding how to adjust the principles. The author has broken down the original ten ER principles into five areas and added some brief advice for each one that has proven to be successful in the 10 years he has been teaching ER at junior high school, senior high school and university in Japan.

Reading Material

- 1 The reading material is easy
- 2 A variety of reading material on a wide range of topics must be available
 - Choose material below students' normal reading level
 - Few or no unfamiliar items of vocabulary or grammar
 - Sets of books can be good but have a variety of series
 - You need a minimum of 3 books per student
 - Include a variety of genres including non-fiction

Learner's choice & goals

- 3 Learners choose what they want to read
- 4 Learners read as much as possible
 - Allow students to choose both which level and which books to read
 - One book per week or a set amount of words per semester/course

Purpose

- 5 The purpose of reading is usually related to pleasure, information and general understanding
- 6 Reading is its own reward
 - Use follow-up activities such as book talks, recommendations & discussions
 - There are no or minimal tests and/or book reports
 - If quizzes must be used, the Moodle Reader is highly recommended

Reading style

7 Reading speed is usually faster rather than slower

8 Reading is individual and silent

Start by having sustained silent reading (SSR) during class time

Gradually move to set the reading as homework

Consider adding a Speed Reading course to your class

Teacher's role

9 Teachers orient and guide their students

10 The teacher is a role model of a reader

Help students select books

Read yourself during SSR to show your love of reading

Apart from the above recommendations on the implementation of the principles of ER there are also a lot of resources and advice available for starting an ER program. The Japan Association for Language Teaching (JALT) ER Special Interest Group has collected some of the major ones on their website (www.ersig.org/drupal-ersig/links) and in 2010 Oxford published an excellent book written by ten different researchers and practitioners on different aspects of ER (Day et al, 2010). Good luck with your ER program.

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Applicable levels: Junior high school, senior high school, university

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